

FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE FUNCTIONS IN LATE ADULTHOOD AND OLD AGE

Absalimova Shoxsanam Muxammadaminovna –
Senior Lecturer of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute.

Abstract: *The period of late adulthood is often referred to as gerontogenesis, or the period of aging. Most researchers believe that this time in a person's life begins at the age of 60. Some authors believe that in women this period begins at 55, and in men from 60 years. People who have reached this age are divided into three subgroups: the elderly, senile age and centenarians. The main feature of this age is the aging process, which is a genetically programmed process, accompanied by certain age-related changes in the body.*

Key words: *Social adaptation of children, difficulties in adaptation, vocational training, educational activities, socio-pedagogical research.*

Аннотация: *Период поздней взрослости часто называют геронтогенезом, или периодом старения. Большинство исследователей считает, что это время в жизни человека начинается с 60 лет. Некоторые авторы полагают, что у женщин данный период начинается с 55, а у мужчин с 60 лет. Люди, достигшие данного возраста, подразделяются на три подгруппы: люди пожилого возраста, старческого возраста и долгожители. Главной особенностью данного возраста является процесс старения, который представляет собой генетически запрограммированный процесс, сопровождающийся определенными возрастными изменениями в организме.*

Ключевые слова: *Социальная адаптация детей, затруднения адаптации, профессиональная подготовка, образовательная деятельность, социально-педагогические исследования.*

The period of late adulthood is often referred to as gerontogenesis, or the period of aging. Most researchers believe that this time in a person's life begins at the age of 60. Some authors believe that in women this period begins at 55, and in men from 60 years. People who have reached this age are divided into three subgroups: the elderly, senile age and centenarians.

The main feature of this age is the aging process, which is a genetically programmed process, accompanied by certain age-related changes in the body.

First of all, there is a gradual weakening of the body's activity. People who have reached late adulthood are no longer so physically strong, their total energy supply becomes significantly less compared to their younger years. The activity of the vascular and immune systems of a person worsens. The vitality of the tissues of the body is lost, which is closely related to a decrease in their fluid content and causes hardening of the joints.

Age-related dehydration, in turn, leads to dry skin. It becomes more sensitive to irritation and sunburn, loses its softness and becomes matte. Aging can be a period of loss or loss (economic, social, individual) that leads to a state of dependence, often perceived as humiliating and painful. But in the positive version, old age is a generalization of experience, knowledge and personal potential, helping to solve the problem of adaptation to the new requirements of life and age-related changes. In the period of old age, one can deeply understand and understand life as a whole, its essence and meaning, its obligations to previous and subsequent generations.

It is very difficult to determine the chronological boundaries of the onset of old age, since the range of individual differences in the appearance of signs of aging is huge. These signs are expressed in a gradual decrease in the functional capabilities of the human body. However, old age should be characterized not only from the negative side, highlighting the extinction of certain abilities in comparison with maturity. It is necessary to establish qualitative differences in the psyche of an elderly person, to identify and show the features of mental development that occurs against the

background of deteriorating psychophysiology, in conditions of involuntional changes in the nervous system. There is a great interest in the study of old age in world science. As a social category, old age, according to F. Aries, was singled out only in the 20th century.

This is caused primarily by the demographic situation that has been developing on planet Earth in the last 100 years. The world population is aging; an increase in the proportion of older people in the population, especially evident in highly developed countries. Among the reasons for the aging of the population are a reduction in the birth rate, improved health care, a decrease in the death rate in infancy and older ages, and an increase in individual life expectancy. The historical trend of increasing life expectancy was most clearly manifested in the last century. The average life expectancy in the Bronze Age was only 18-20 years, in the Middle Ages - 35 years, in the XIX century. - 44 years old. In the XX century. average life expectancy has risen to 68-72 years. At the same time, with almost every generation, the normal individual life expectancy also increases. The phenomenon of the aging of the population, the transformation of society into a "graying", into a "world of old people", gives rise to new medical, financial, legal, political and other issues and problems. A significant part of the voters and consumers of goods and services is now the elderly, which requires a certain reorientation of the entire system. Increasingly, we see political and commercial advertisements specifically targeted at older people. The most acute problem is the organization of pensions and social support in old age, which requires large material resources (and this means an increase in the burden on working members of society) and human resources (a huge army of social workers). Even the economically stable states of Europe and America believe that it will be more and more difficult for them to solve this problem (it is even called the "demographic time bomb"). Some states have already raised the issue of revising the retirement age (for example, in the UK after 2010 the retirement age for women will increase to 65 years). Old age as an age period has become a

mass phenomenon; it is quite realistic to live another 15 to 20 years after retirement, which is approximately a quarter of life. Aging is seen as both a social and a personal problem. The knowledge of the laws of aging, the expansion of the age limits of active work capacity and full life, the development of ways to optimize aging is the most important complex problem of gerontology, gerontomedicine, and gerontopsychology. Gerontopsychology is a branch of developmental psychology devoted to the problems of aging, which has recently emerged and is not sufficiently developed, but has attracted increasing attention from researchers in recent decades. How does mental aging proceed? far from a complete list of questions.

There are many approaches to understanding and studying old age. It is very important to be aware of the basic idea of old age that underlies this or that approach, since the specificity of the perception of old age simultaneously dictates a range of theoretical issues and prescribes ways to solve numerous practical problems. Old age as a basic biological property of all living organisms is considered in the theories of “programmed” and “programmed” aging, in the theories of “wear and tear”, “cellular waste”, aging of the immune system and cytological theory. Each of these theories substantiates its own model of the body's aging mechanism. Biological theories include the theory of the founder of Russian gerontology A.A. Bogomolets, who considered the violation of the harmony of the physiological processes of the body to be the main factor in aging, and the theory of aging as intoxication by I.I. Mechnikov. Gerontologist V.V. Frolkis defined old age as a time of reduction in the adaptive capabilities of the organism. Analyzing the fundamental mechanisms of aging, Frolkis not only stated the fact of a decrease in the adaptive capabilities of the body, but showed self-regulation tendencies that resist destruction and are aimed at stabilizing the body's vital activity and increasing life expectancy. The concept of anti-aging, or vitaukta (from Latin vita - life, auktum - increase), is an important aspect of the adaptive-regulatory theory of aging he proposed.

The approach based on the notion of aging programmed by evolution, included in the genetic code ("Programmed aging"), and the approach according to which cell damage is not genetically predetermined, but occurs randomly, as a result of failures ("Programmed aging"), are very general biological character in explaining the causes of involution in old age. It is important that, depending on the proposed In the theory of dissociation (the theory of liberation, "exiting the game"), it is considered an inevitable process of the gradual destruction of social ties.

The phenomenon of dissociation is expressed in a change in motivation, in focusing on one's inner world and a decline in communication. Objectively, "dissociation" is manifested in the loss of former social roles, in the deterioration of health, in a decrease in income, in the loss or alienation of loved ones. Subjectively, it is experienced by the individual as uselessness, narrowing the range of interests, focusing them on oneself. The essence of the theory is that the process of desocialization is biologically and psychologically justified and inevitable. mechanism of aging, a system of predictions of the future state of the body is built. The gap between the individual and society occurs shortly after retirement, by inertia, an elderly person continues to maintain old connections, is interested in what is happening at work. Then these connections become more and more artificial and are gradually interrupted. The amount of information received by a person decreases, the range of his interests narrows, activity decreases, and therefore the aging process accelerates. The theory of activity ("new employment") is the opposite of the theory of desocialization; it focuses on the positive relationship between the level of activity and satisfaction with life. Activity theory suggests that old people should be involved in society. The concept of an uninterrupted life path interprets old age as a battlefield for the preservation of the old lifestyle. Social approaches to old age include consideration of more particular problems of the relationship between an old person and other people (members of his family, social workers). These are very topical problems of "assistant tension", cruelty to the elderly, and

domestic violence. Old age as a cognitive problem. This approach is based on the so-called "deficit model" - the process of loss or reduction of emotional and intellectual abilities.

According to the author, the strength of the influence of factors differs depending on age. In old age, the influence of normative age factors is great, and it is necessary to take into account the accumulated effect of non-normative personal events. The Baltes model allows you to clearly distinguish what is typical in the development of all people, what is common for specific generations, and what is special in the life of an individual

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